

Issue: 4 pp: 768-773

JEL Codes: L8, Z2

HANG Y., ZHONG Y., HUILI S. (2020). "Research on the Quality Assurance System of
College High-level Sports Teams in Guangdong Province", Vol: 1 Issue: 4 pp: 768-773

Key Words: Guangdong universities; High-level sports teams; The quality of school running; Insurance system.

Article Type Review Article

**Research on the Quality Assurance System of College High-level Sports Teams in
Guangdong Province**

Arrived Date
27.08.2020

Accepted Date
03.09.2020

Published Date
31.10.2020

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ABSTRACT

This research uses the literature material method, expert interview method, field survey method, questionnaire survey method, mathematical statistics, logic analysis method to carry out high level sports teams of colleges and universities in Guangdong were investigated, by understanding the schools implement national policies and high level sports teams of sports special immortal, educational policy, to research and analysis of the various universities sports educational situation. The focus of this study is mainly to explore the school-running quality problem, the high level sports teams in colleges and universities high level sports teams of running a school for students, the school management department, the department in charge of sports, such as teachers and coaches subject of investigation, and the national policies and the schools of sports special immortal, high level sports teams in school policies are analyzed, and put forward the corresponding high level sports team education quality insurance system.

Introduction

For high-level sports teams in colleges, the characteristics are that students of the teams lack behind in non-sports courses, the learning time is limited due to training and competition, training is difficult to be separated from the authority and the faculty, and the teaching quality management is difficult. Undoubtedly, this will bring new challenges to higher education. More than 20 years of trials of high-level sports teams in Chinese universities have proved that there are many problems as well as achievements. College high-level sports teams are for making up our the problems of "the Whole Nation System" in sports. Based on this aspect, this study talks about how to establish a more reasonable quality assurance system for college high-level sports teams so as to achieve better results in education quality and sports performance, and this is also the meaning of the study.

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Objects of the Research

The objects of the research are the college high-level sports teams in Guangdong Province. The research will look into their enrollment mode, team management, policy implementation, learning and competition training arrangement, employment security and other aspects to ensure the sustainable development of high-level sports and puts forward a corresponding quality assurance system.

Methods of the Research

Literature Materials Method

By referring to relevant papers, books and other relevant materials, the authors conducted a preliminary analysis of the results, so as to provide reference for this paper.

Interview Method

the authors consulted the competent departments of colleges and universities in Guangdong Province, the competent departments of universities and related experts and scholars for the relevant situation of high-level sports teams in colleges and universities. After this, the authors integrated their opinions into this research paper.

Field Investigation Method

The authors went to various colleges and universities in Guangdong to conduct field investigation to learn about each school's views on the relevant policies for high-level sports teams, enrollment, training, students and teachers' opinions, so that the authors can access information needed.

Questionnaire Method

Before designing the questionnaire, the authors read a lot of related books and literature on sports, social surveys, and related literature. Combining the important issues of this theme, the authors designed a "Questionnaire on the Status Quo of the Quality of High-level Sports Teams in Colleges and Universities"

Mathematical Statistics Method

According to the research purpose, the authors classified and summarized the effective data obtained during the research process, and used SPSS17.0 software and Excel for calculation and analysis to ensure a reasonable and reliable research.

Logical Analysis Method

By combing the status quo of the quality of high-level sports teams, the authors compared and summarized various factors that affect the quality, thus forming an analysis and thinking on this aspect.

Research Results and Analysis

Analysis of the Status Quo of High-level Sports Teams in Guangdong

Cultivating high-level sports teams has developed into a special education model of higher education, which involves many people. It is the guarantee for the sustainable development of national competitive sports. At the same time, it is of great significance in helping professional athletes to develop their careers after retirement, improving college students' sports level, enriching campus life, improving the ranking of Chinese college students in world college sports competitions, and ensuring the sustainable development of competitive sports in China.

The Status Quo of High-level Sports Teams Members

Most of these students have professional sports experience, but they perform poorly in the school curriculum. With the increase of age and the maturity of self-awareness, many sports students realize the importance of cultural knowledge and want to convert knowledge into skills and enrich their knowledge reserves by studying professional knowledge at university. But these students have insufficient knowledge reserves, which makes the learning process more difficult. This can easily lead to a situation where students win in sports competitions, but they lag behind in class. This is a major factor affecting students' academic self-confidence.

High-level sports team students often continue to train and participate in competitions after entering colleges. In order to improve the level of training and encourage students to get better rankings in the competition, some schools have a training program with a long cycle, dense frequency and high intensity. This will bring greater challenges to students who need help in their studies. At the same time, fatigue and difficulty of learning are double tests for these students.

The Basic Situation of the Management of College High-level Sports Teams in Guangdong

The Way of Arrangement

Due to the expansion of colleges and universities and the continuous increase of high-level sports team projects, the competition of limited student resources has made competition in policies such as admission, teaching, and management more intense; some schools have unified class teaching for these sports students; some schools let these students choose majors they like; some schools arrange teachers to the sports base to teach them; some schools conduct correspondence teaching and online teaching or make use of holidays to teach.

Colleges and universities have relatively consistent requirements for the content of the entrance examinations and admission qualifications for these students; the requirements for training and competitions that athletes need to participate in on time after registration are also relatively similar. But there are also many differences. Each school has its own focus on the construction and goals of high-level sports teams, the management system of the sports teams, the investment of human resources and funds, and work plans.

Teaching Management

In this regard, there are still many problems. For example, in order to improve the school's athletic performance, many schools pay more attention to sports training and the construction and improvement of sports teams, while reducing the number of students' courses. Some schools reduce the number of required credits. Some schools reduce the number of hours of related courses. What's more, some schools reduce the difficulty of courses. These practices make it difficult to guarantee the quality of these students' learning.

Majors and Curriculum

In this regard, there are many problems. For example, students learn poorly in courses; study time is restricted by training and competition; physical training and department teaching are often the same group; teaching management is difficult. These will undoubtedly bring new challenges to higher education. At present, colleges and universities in Guangdong Province basically follow the principles of strong practicality and low requirements for basic cultural knowledge in the selection of majors for these students. On this basis, students can choose their own majors within the specified range, or the education department will arrange majors for them, so as to facilitate management. In terms of curriculum settings, in view of the widespread existence of these students' lack of curriculum performance and weak learning ability, many schools will also adjust their curriculum settings. For example, schools will increase basic knowledge courses and professional elective courses.

Schools' Situation of High-level Sports Team Students Participating in Training Competitions and Learning Management

After the athlete students register for admission, in addition to course study, they are also athletes. Each school has different preferential policies for these students, such as tuition reduction or exemption, scholarships, etc. This greatly stimulated their enthusiasm for learning and training. In terms of sports training arrangements, most colleges and universities have clear requirements for the frequency of training and participation in competitions. Some schools use half a day for training and half a day for class; some schools use their spare time to organize sports training; When there is a conflict between competition training and course learning, most school documents indicate that time adjustments will be made before major competitions. Schools often arrange 1-2 weeks for intensive training time for sports students. Some schools will adjust the class time during the competition training period, such as training during the day and class at night. There are also very few schools that cut the number of courses in half

one semester in advance, and even suspended students from training. Some schools will also adopt corresponding policies in the evaluation of students' performance, such as giving students extra points for examinations, exemptions from courses, and exemptions from examinations based on the results of sports competitions. Or, based on student training and competition, schools will give extra points to the course.

Investigation on the Attitudes of Students from High-level Sports Teams to Employment

For these students' ideas about employment, this content includes two parts. The first part is the students at school. Most colleges and universities have set their majors before entering the school. These majors are often practical and have low requirements for basic education, such as business administration and marketing. It is not difficult for students to learn these courses. Generally speaking, athletes have good psychological quality and are more likely to accept the content of the course when they are learning in a practical-oriented course. This is conducive to enhancing self-confidence in learning and stimulating interest in learning, so as to prepare students for completing graduation requirements and engaging in related professional work after graduation. The second part is graduates, these people now have jobs. According to the collected questionnaire data, many graduates are still engaged in occupations related to their sports.

Thoughts on the Quality Assurance System of High-level Sports Teams in Colleges and Universities in Guangdong Province

The quality assurance system is an organic whole of quality management. This system aims to improve and guarantee product quality, and this system will use systematic methods to closely organize the quality control activities of related departments and links. Since the mid-1990s, the quality assurance system has been introduced into the category of higher education research, and has quickly become a hot issue in higher education research. At present, the research on higher education quality assurance system mainly focuses on higher education evaluation and supervision, teacher team building, and education quality concepts. At the same time, the system will also consider the market's demand for talents. However, as a new branch of the education model, high-level sports teams are still pilot projects. This kind of education model is different from general higher education in terms of students' learning foundation, identity, and psychology, as well as the school's teaching model.

Reasonable School Model

Colleges and universities need to carry out appropriate reforms and make overall plans on the existing school-running models. That is to optimize the structure of the school form to improve the quality of the sports team. On the basis of the existing high-level sports team development plan, colleges and universities should continuously optimize the layout of the education model.

Standardize Teaching and Training Management

Student athletes have two roles. They are both athletes and students. Schools should take effective measures to improve the education level of athletes and ensure that high-level athlete students can complete their learning tasks in accordance with relevant academic regulations. Schools can provide relevant assistance based on the characteristics of athletes participating in training and competitions, such as adding basic knowledge courses, adding professional elective courses, or helping to customize training programs. The purpose of these measures is to help student athletes successfully complete their studies.

Strengthen the Professional Level and Management of Coaches

In students' daily learning and training, the role of the coach is very important. The professional knowledge and sports experience of the coaches can provide guidance for students. Colleges and universities should pay attention to improving the professional level of coaches of high-level sports teams, and continuously enhance the professional quality and scientific training level of coaches, so as to provide a good foundation for maintaining and improving students' competitive ability. At the same time, each school needs to establish a coaching file system, implement a certification system, and strengthen coach training. All schools should establish professional title assessment mechanisms that

are directly linked to competition results, which can greatly improve the motivation of coaches.

Improve the Effectiveness of the Competent Authority

All competent departments must take their own responsibilities and cooperate with each other. This can guarantee the quality of education received by athletes under the "Whole Nation System" after their retirement. At the same time, in today's knowledge economy, this can also help ensure that this school model achieves sustainable development.

Establish A Sound Sports Injury Insurance Mechanism

A sound accidental injury insurance mechanism not only reduces the pressure on coaches and athletes, but also effectively protects and prolongs the careers of athletes. Through investigation and research, some schools have stipulated that schools must purchase personal accident insurance for all athletes, and this regulation has been implemented.

Conclusions and Suggestions

Conclusions

Students generally register for admission through additional physical examinations or separate examinations, and they have certain professional sports experience. Most students want to learn professional knowledge in university and apply what they learn to their future work. However, learning difficulties and setbacks are an important factor affecting these students' confidence in learning.

For the admission of athletes, the examination content and admission requirements of each school are roughly the same. The difference is that each school has its own different inclination and considerations for sports team goals and development plans, management systems, human resources and capital investment.

Athlete students of various colleges and universities have different preferential policies, such as tuition reduction or exemption, scholarships, and bonuses for athletes. These measures have greatly stimulated the enthusiasm of students. In terms of curriculum settings, if there is a conflict between training competitions, class and examination time, each school has corresponding reasonable arrangements. After athletes enroll, most schools have clear requirements and corresponding reward and punishment mechanisms in terms of training frequency and participation in competitions. The purpose of these measures is to maintain the enthusiasm of sports students in training, help improve their competitive level, and bring honors to the school and the team.

For these students' ideas about employment, this content includes two parts. The first part is the students at school. Most colleges and universities have set their majors before entering the school. These majors are often practical and have low requirements for basic education, such as business administration and marketing. It is not difficult for students to learn these courses. Generally speaking, athletes have good psychological quality and are more likely to accept the content of the course when they are learning in a practical-oriented course. This is conducive to enhancing self-confidence in learning and stimulating interest in learning, so as to prepare students for completing graduation requirements and engaging in related professional work after graduation. The second part is graduates, these people now have jobs. According to the collected questionnaire data, many graduates are still engaged in occupations related to their sports.

Suggestions

Each school should optimize its structure on the existing model. That is, schools need to reform within the existing sports team development framework to improve the quality of high-level sports teams.

Schools can provide relevant assistance based on the characteristics of athletes participating in training and competitions, such as adding basic knowledge courses, adding professional elective courses, or helping to customize training programs. The purpose of these measures is to help student athletes successfully complete their studies.

Colleges and universities should pay attention to improving the professional level of coaches of high-

level sports teams, and continuously enhance the professional quality and scientific training level of coaches, so as to provide a good foundation for maintaining and improving students' competitive ability. At the same time, coaches should constantly update training methods and content to stimulate students' enthusiasm for training. The purpose of this move is to make students more actively participate in training.

Schools should establish and improve the management system and operating mechanism of high-level sports teams. Schools should form a leading group responsible for coordinating the development, planning and management of the sports team. At the same time, relevant functional departments and departments should take up their responsibilities and coordinate with each other. This can help them to do a good job in the construction and management of high-level sports teams in cooperation.

For athletes, sports injuries in training and competition are inevitable. Therefore, it is very important to establish a sound sports injury insurance mechanism. This not only reduces the pressure of coaches and athletes, but also effectively protects and prolongs the athletes' sports career.

Source of the project: Guangdong Philosophy and Social Science Planning Project (Project Number: GD14XT11)

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